

SOIL CARBON DIOXIDE EVOLUTION IN RESPONSE TO AGRICULTURAL LAND USE

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Abstract

Global climate change due to greenhouse effect induced by the increase in the atmospheric carbon dioxide is one of the problems confronting this generation. Agricultural land use has been implicated as one of the sources of carbon dioxide emission into the atmosphere. This study investigates the influence of land use on the emission of CO₂ from the soil. Using a static chamber method with the use of alkali to trap CO₂, the CO₂ emission from a maize farm subjected to different management was investigated. An experimental plot originally set up to evaluate the influence of the use of difference bush fallow species on soil quality and maize yield was evaluated. The treatment consisted of Pueraria, Panicum, Euphorbia, natural fallow and natural fallow with fertilizer all of which were ploughed under and then planted to maize. Carbon dioxide emission was monitored during the period when the plots were under maize cultivation. The result showed that there were no significant differences in the CO₂ evolved among the treatments. However, the CO₂ emission was found to be positively influenced by soil water content and soil temperature. This study demonstrated that arable agricultural soil may contribute as much as 14-18 t ha⁻¹ of CO₂ annually to the atmospheric CO₂ load. By careful manipulation of the soil temperature regime through canopy cover or through some vegetated means it may be possible to reduce CO₂ emission from agricultural soils.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing global warming which is a challenge to this generation has been ascribed to the increased concentration of the greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. This is mainly due to activities of man such as CO₂ from the burning of fossil fuels and from agricultural activities. Conversion of forested land to agriculture, bush burning, swamp rice cultivation and ruminant animals production among others have been implicated in the production greenhouse gases. Carbon is stored in the soil as organic matter and is respired by plants, bacteria, fungi and animals. Release of CO₂ from the soil occurs through different processes such as microbial decomposition of SOM and root respiration which together is referred to as soil respiration. Soil respiration has been identified to play a significant role and as well as being a driver for climate change. It can be partitioned to root respiration, microbial respiration, as they consume the labile carbohydrates exudates from plant roots, decomposing litters and oxidation of soil organic matter. Decomposition of litters is responsible for a greater part of soil respiration (Wang et al., 1999). Soils altogether contain an estimated 1,700 Gt (billion metric tons) to a depth of 1 m and as much as 2,400 Gt to a depth of 2 m. An estimated additional 560 Gt is contained in terrestrial biota (plants and animals). In contrast, the carbon in the atmosphere is estimated to total 750 Gt. Thus, the amount of organic carbon in soils is more than four times the amount of carbon in terrestrial biota and three times that in the atmosphere (Cox et al., 2000; Hillel and Rosenzweig, 2009). Researchers have estimated that soil respiration accounts for 77 Gt of carbon released to the atmosphere each year. This level of release is one order of magnitude greater

than the carbon released due to anthropogenic sources (6 Gt per year) such as fossil fuel burning. Alteration of soil conditions such as moisture content, aeration and temperature to a large extent determine soil biological activities and hence both the potential of soil to either release carbon as CO₂ to store it as SOM (Almagro et al., 2008). It is generally agreed that only soil offer the potential to mitigate atmospheric CO₂ by sequestering it as carbon over a short time period. All other methods will take several years before they can bring about any noticeable change in atmospheric carbon dioxide level (West and Marland, 2001; Hillel and Rosenzweig, 2009). Agricultural soils therefore play a key role in C cycling by acting as either source or sink of C and thereby impacting greenhouse emissions (Paustian et al., 1997; Dumansk et al., 1998; Berroux et al., 2002). There can be no simple universal prescriptions regarding practices to manage soils so as to help mitigate the greenhouse effect. While the basic principles can be stated in universal terms, their application to different sites will require specific adjustments (Hillel and Rosenzweig, 2009). The Kyoto Protocol however affirms that part of the CO₂ emissions from fossil-fuel use and from other sources, can be offset by removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere via a net increase in the C stocks of the biosphere. Emissions offsets via reforestation and afforestation are endorsed by the Kyoto Protocol now, and sequestration service by farmers and other landowners could provide a source of C-emission credits to be sold to emitters of C and hence provide an additional source of income for farmers (West and Marland, 2001). In sub-Sahara Africa, little efforts have been made to quantify the extent of CO₂ emission resulting from different agricultural landuse. This is required to be able to effectively trade in C stock under the clean development mechanism (CDM). In several of the developed countries of the world, the potentials of different types of land use and different levels of input to either sequester or to release CO₂ are already clearly documented and are being used by farmers to negotiate for C sales. However in Nigeria, there is a dearth of information on the association between different agricultural landuse and the level of carbon released as CO₂ or sequestered as SOM under different types of agricultural land management. In Nigeria, like other developing economies, there is little data available on the potential of different land use management practices on the magnitude of C stored or released from the soil. It has therefore not been possible to evaluate the quantity of C stored under these landuse management practices such as practiced in these developing countries. This has not enabled farmers in these countries to participate actively like their counterparts in the developed economies in carbon trading. The objective of this study is to determine the relationships between some soil properties to soil CO₂ evolution and to quantify the contributions different agricultural land use to the release of CO₂ from soil.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The field experiment was carried out at Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching and Research Farm (T&RF), Ile-Ife (latitude 7°25' N, and longitude 4°39'E), Nigeria. It is located in the rainforest ecosystem in the southwestern region of Nigeria with a mean annual rainfall of about 1400 mm which is bimodally distributed with peaks in June and September. Average annual insolation/radiation is 18.7 MJ m⁻² day⁻¹. The soil derived from coarse grained granite and gneisses is classified at series level as

two series (Smyth and Montgomery, 1962) and as Oxic Haplustult and Ferric Acrisol respectively according to USDA Soil Taxonomy and WRB soil classification systems (Nwachokor and Uzu, 2008). The soil is well drained with the surface texture varying from sandy loam to sandy clay loam. It was located on a 1-2 % slope. The 0.7 ha experimental field was previously cultivated to different fallow species to determine the effects of controlled fallow on soil properties and the yield of succeeding maize crops (See Tijani et al., 2008 for full description). The fallow treatments were: NNF (native fallow), NFF (native fallow with addition of fertilizers during cropping), PAF (*Panicum maximum* J.), EUF (*Euphorbia heterophyllum* L.), and PUF (*Pueraria phaseoloides* B.). The treatments were replicated four times. The static chamber method was used to measure CO₂ flux. It consisted of a 13-litre transparent plastic container. The container was pushed into the soil to a depth of 5 mm at each of the sites. A solution of 0.5 M NaOH in a beaker was placed inside the plastic container to trap the CO₂ evolved from the soil. The NaOH was removed after 2 hours and immediately titrated against 0.5 M H₂SO₄ to determine the CO₂ absorbed. Measurements were taken twice during the growing season and compared with an adjacent undisturbed forest. At the time of determination, the soil moisture content, pH, temperature and the organic matter content at each sampling point were determined. Soil samples collected at each sampling date were analysed for pH in water (1:1) using an ISFET pH meter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil properties

There was no significant difference in soil moisture content under the different treatments (Table 1). This is apparently because the effects of previous fallow treatments had waned after it was tilled and then subjected to uniform maize cultivation. The soil temperature early in the season was however highest under both plots that were ~~under~~ previously under *Pueraria* and *Panicum* fallows. The darker coloration of these soils consequence upon higher soil organic matter (SOM) contents could have resulted in the absorption of more sunlight thus raising the soil temperature. This is more so at the early stages when the cultivated maize had not established enough cover to shield the soil surface from the heat of the sun. Soil pH was significantly lowest (5.90) on the plot that was treated with inorganic fertilizer after previous native fallow. Nitrogen based inorganic fertilizers have long been associated with soil acidification in the savannah ecosystems of Nigeria (Singh and Balasubramanian, 1979). This modification of the soil reaction is expected to influence the soil biota and hence the SOM dynamics. Both the control (forest) and *Pueraria* plots however had the highest soil pH levels. The soil water content at the second sampling during the late season (Table 2) followed a similar pattern as that in the early season with no significant difference among the treatments. Soil temperature was however significantly lowest under the forest while there was no significant difference among the other treatments. This is because at the late maturing stage, the maize had established a uniform canopy cover across all the treatments. Lower soil temperature recorded under the forest was due to a much higher canopy cover under the forest gallery consisting of vegetation cover at different heights thus achieving maximum soil cover. Soil pH at the second sampling also followed a similar trend as

the first season. There was however the soil pH at late season was lower than at early season across all the treatments.

Carbon dioxide evolution

The carbon dioxide evolved from the cultivated soils ranged from about 15 t ha⁻¹ to about 18 t ha⁻¹. This amount is by a magnitude of 2 higher than the amount released from the forest soil. However, previous fallow had no significant effect on the magnitude of CO₂ evolved from the soil after it was cropped to maize. This again may be attributed to the uniform effect of tillage and the cultivation of maize monocrop. The early season measurement was significantly lower than the late season values. This may be ascribed to lower soil moisture contents coupled with lower temperature at the time of sampling. The late season sampling was done in November which is a period at which the ambient air temperature and hence the soil temperature is generally low. This will expectedly retard the activities of SOM decomposing soil microorganisms.

Correlation between soil properties and CO₂ evolution

The correlation matrix between soil properties and CO₂ evolution is presented in Table 3. Soil water content and temperature were significantly ($p < 0.01$) with soil CO₂ release. This relationship is similar to earlier findings. Almegro et al. (2008) observed positive relationships between soil CO₂ efflux and both soil water content and temperature. They concluded that while temperature is important when the soil is uniformly wet, soil moisture became more important during the dry summer periods such as experienced in the Mediterranean regions. The relationships between soil temperature and soil CO₂ efflux however have been found to be exponential (Hoshimoto et al., 2009). This is in consonance with earlier findings of Fang and Moncrieff (2001).

CONCLUSIONS

The study quantified the CO₂ efflux from arable agricultural soils showed that increased soil water content and temperature are driving factors for its release from arable agricultural soils. It also demonstrated that the conversion of forest to conventional arable cultivations more than doubled the release of CO₂ from the soil. Thus measures that keeps the soil temperature down while ensuring minimum soil disturbance has a promise of reducing soil CO₂ efflux. Therefore agricultural practices such as the planting of cover crops, no tillage and the use mulch and other measures to keep the soil temperature minimal are recommended for greenhouse mitigation in such agricultural soils.

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